

Localized and Limited-Dispersive Delivery of Thermal Stimuli to Liquid Crystal Oligomer Networks Through Radio-Frequency Media

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Wireless energy transmission (WET) promises to enhance device mobility through selective and untethered energy delivery. In this paper, WET principles are harnessed to directly and non-dispersively transfer thermal stimuli to designated areas within thermally-responsive liquid crystal oligomer networks (LCONs). For this, a conductive coil receiver within the LCON as a remote stimuli source is embedded. Upon activation by radio-frequency WET, targeted Joule heating occurs and the low thermal conductivity of LCONs causes retention of delivered stimulus at the receiver, generating temperature differences of up to 45 °C within the host LCON. This enables localized LCON actuation and self-regulated oscillations with a natural frequency of ≈ 0.027 Hz. WET selectivity is further demonstrated within self-pressing buttons for keyboards, where actuation only in designated areas is required for operation. The work is envisioned to contribute toward remote material-based logic for hybrid circuit designs for medical, soft robotic, and haptic applications.

1. Introduction

Wireless energy transmission (WET) offers expanded functionality, mobility, and new prospects in handling energy in electronic devices.^[1] In fact, the potential of WET can be expanded beyond its current conventional induction heating, communication and networking applications by its utilization to directly drive responsive systems.^[2] For instance, the activation of self-folding materials through WET demonstrated the application of the selectivity of WET.^[3] This concept is expressed in the materials domain through the coupling of WET with responsive, or smart, materials.^[4] For interactive materials, such as liquid crystal polymers, where molecular alignment can be disturbed thermally to induce deformation, the possibility of WET-based remote actuation through induction heating has

been shown.^[5] Conversely, the implementation of responsive liquid crystal polymers to control the direction of transmitted wireless power has also been achieved, marking the synergies between functions.^[6] Yet, synergies between WET drivers and smart materials can be further utilized to derive conditionally selective and localized energy delivery for remote-controlled interactive materials. This would contribute toward the development of miniaturized multi-functional single-material devices for soft robots and haptics.^[7]

The programmable actuation and compliance of liquid crystal polymers in response to photonic, thermal and electrical stimuli has put them in the spotlight for interactive functions.^[8] For instance, they have been applied as an integral smart component to produce bio-mimicking soft actuators, where the compliant nature of the material allows for effective interaction with people or the wider world.^[9] Furthermore, more like a living organism, the intrinsic properties of responsive liquid crystal oligomer networks (LCONs) have been applied to produce basic material-based logic, promising matching or pronounced behavior when combined with selective energy delivery through WET;^[10] the term LCON denotes the initial oligomeric structure of the material before final cross-linking, avoiding ambiguity between liquid crystal networks and liquid crystal elastomers in terms of glass transition temperature and Young's Modulus, since these properties can be made to vary greatly based on

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Figure 1. c-LCON compositing and function. A) Illustration of c-LCON synthesis and compositing process, including (i) schematics of Molecules 1–5 included in the reaction mixture for our LCON material, (ii) representation of the receiver coil embedding process within LCON material during curing and (iii) depiction of c-LCON after primary curing of the material with the embedded receiver coil composited. B) Annotated schematics for the processing of c-LCON material into a button configuration, showing the (i) stamping process and (ii) LC alignment of the c-LCON before and (iii) after the stamping process. C) Footage of the c-LCON button and corresponding IR measurement during WET operation, depicting state (i) before and (ii) after actuation. WET parameters were set to 2 MHz, while the transmitter was placed in parallel, and 7 mm apart, to the plane of the receiver coil.

liquid crystal composition. Building on the responsive properties of LCON materials, limited-dispersive energy delivery to only electrically-designated areas would allow for sole activation of selected areas on demand, translating into more intricate actuation control of remote-controlled interactive material systems.^[11] Combining radio-frequency-WET and LCON actuation enables electronically-safe operation and high LCON deformation; moreover, the compliant properties of LCONs allow for a higher compatibility with users in human interactive functions, compared to traditional machinery.

Thus, in our work, we introduce localized and selective energy delivery to our LCON materials in response to a WET stimulus. This is realized by embedding a polyimide-coated copper coil into our LCONs (c-LCONs). The embedded receiver extracts energy from the applied WET stimulus and then transfers it to the surrounding LCON environment thermally. The thermal conductivity of LCONs is anisotropic, which can cause variation of up to 20-fold magnitude between the aligned and non-aligned directions at room temperature, yet these variables are dependent on order parameters.^[12] Low LCON thermal conductivity effectively traps the thermal actuation stimulus within the c-LCON itself and impacts its local area primarily. We applied this selective and limited-dispersive stimuli transfer behavior to build electronically functionalized, self-regulating c-LCON oscillators.

We expanded this demonstration to showcase local energy delivery through a remote-activated c-LCON keyboard, which requires this material property to function. We envision our work will contribute toward the application of advanced mobile intelligent materials in remote electronically-driven environments, such as smart haptics in virtual reality, as the electrical stimuli source can now be physically separated from the active material.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Wireless Energy Transfer Memory Material Construction

Our WET memory materials consist of a liquid crystal diacrylate, labeled Molecule 1, synthesized into a polymer through the two-step curing method using tetra-thiols, di-thiols, tetra-vinyls and photoinitiator, labeled Molecules 2–5 in Figure 1A(i) and analyzed in Figure S1 (Supporting Information).^[13] Our reactive mesogen reaction mixture was optimized for its low-temperature phase transitions and subsequently low-temperature actuation response, initiating at ≈ 15 °C. Specifically, this was achieved by the use of short-benzoic core liquid crystal mesogens and vinyl additions to reduce the quality of liquid crystal order and the resulting temperature threshold for actuation. This is performed in exchange for overall actuation capacity and kinetics, as is shown

in the comparisons with the vinyl-addition and non-vinyl variants of our LCONs in the supporting information. A 5 mm polyimide-coated copper flat coil receiver is submerged within the reaction mixture during the primary curing stage. This encapsulates the receiver within our material as polymerization occurs around it, as illustrated in Figure 1A(ii,iii). The embedded coils cause mechanical stress fields in their surrounding c-LCON environment, as detected in Figure S2 (Supporting Information); hence, we designed the button configuration, as depicted in Figure 1B, to minimize these effects on actuation. Stamping our c-LCON materials into columnar buttons before the final curing stage, as shown in Figure 1B(i), introduces higher order-parameter liquid crystal (LC) alignment into the LCON material because it is mechanically strained in its nematic phase.^[14] Due to the alignment director conforming to the direction of applied strain, the button configuration results in an LC alignment parallel to the button walls and perpendicular to the receiver placement, as observed in Figure S3 (Supporting Information) and explained in Figure 1B(ii,iii) respectively. This LC molecular alignment profile was selected to maximize the actuation of the c-LCON. The induced alignment was arrested in the material by further cross-linking the network using a photo-initiator molecule, known as Irgacure 819, in the second curing stage. Therefore, upon loss of LC molecular order, our c-LCON buttons have the capability to contract into the platform and “press” themselves; this process is reversed upon the removal of the stimuli disturbing the LC molecular order. c-LCON button “presses” can be triggered by the application of a thermal stimulus delivered through WET, as shown in Figure 1C and Video S1 (Supporting Information), because thermal energy induces vibrations of LC molecules to disturb their alignment.^[15]

2.2. Selective Stimuli Delivery Through Wireless Energy Transfer

Through WET, thermal stimuli can be delivered to designated areas within our c-LCONs in a limited-dispersive manner. Upon exposing our c-LCONs to a radio-frequency stimulus, the embedded receiver harvests energy and releases it thermally through Joule heating, inducing a maximum temperature difference of 43 °C within an LCON in a 12 °C refrigerated environment. The nematic-to-isotropic phase transition of our LCON formulation begins at 15 °C, as shown in Figure S4 (Supporting Information); we observe an average thermal response and relaxation rate of $\approx 1.65\%$ strain per °C and 1.67% per °C, respectively, in our LCON material. Yet, the actuation and relaxation rate of our system was slower than expected, with $\approx 0.19\%$ strain per second and 0.025% per second, respectively. The thermal images and temperature graphic in Figure 2A(i,ii) indicate that the different regions of our LCON have different liquid crystal order parameters simultaneously; this is facilitated by the low thermal conductivity of the LCON. This explains the relatively slow LCON actuation by providing evidence that the receiver experiences a rapid increase in its temperature, up to 40 °C in 8 s, in an environment with an initial starting temperature of 23 °C, while the temperature of the surrounding LCON material is negligibly affected, showing no change in temperature, or only in the surfaces adjacent to the coil with an initial maximum increase of 2 °C. This slow dispersion of the encapsulated actuation stim-

ulus within the c-LCON, or thermal self-shielding of the material, results in the transferred stimulus primarily activating its local area. In the configuration presented in Figure 2A(i,ii), the transferred thermal stimulus gradually disperses across the c-LCON system over a period of 5 min, in sequence of spatial proximity to the embedded receiver as depicted in the heat-map in Figure 2A(i). The effects of this mechanism on actuation are demonstrated through pulsed WET by comparing the c-LCON actuation behavior to their corresponding local LCON temperature profiles, as presented in Figure 2A(ii,iii). These phenomena were simulated by finite element modeling, as illustrated in Figure 2B, to confirm the action of the delayed actuation mechanism and the altitude change of the c-LCON; greater altitude drops are expected for taller button configurations and vice versa. The difference and delay between LCON and receiver temperatures in Figure 2C, marks the limited-dispersive stimuli behavior, of which the stimuli transport period is determined by operating the WET system in a pulsed mode, as shown in Figure 2D. In a typical sample, described in Figure 1B, our c-LCON button has a thermal stimuli transport period of 4.70 ± 0.33 s, based on a series of 5 trials on one sample. When WET is ceased, this thermal stimulus is eventually dispersed across the LCON, leaving local thermal conditions insufficient for LCON actuation and allowing the material to revert to its initial state; the time required for this thermal dispersion is dependent on the amount of energy already delivered to the system by the time WET is stopped.

2.3. Adjusting Stimuli Delivery Through the Wireless Energy Transfer System

The thermal stimulus is delivered to the c-LCON through the operation of our excitation circuit, which consists of a transmitter coil coupled with a class E amplifier; this single-pole switching-mode amplifier design is optimized for radio frequencies through the use of shunt capacitance to create a reactive network between the switch and the load.^[16] An illustration of the device is shown in Figure 3A, and a schematic of its driving parameters and role within the c-LCON-based system is presented in Figure 3B; the design of the excitation circuit is described in Table S1 (Supporting Information) and is further explained in terms of amplifier, transmitter and power output in Figures S5–S7 (Supporting Information), respectively. The efficiency of energy transfer between the transmitter and the receiver in the c-LCON can be described by the coupling efficiency parameter.^[17] For our system, this parameter is dependent on the mutual inductance of the c-LCON receiver and excitation circuit transmitter coils. In turn, mutual inductance between two coils is dependent on their relative coil turns and dimensions. Aiming to miniaturize our system while retaining sufficient mutual inductance, magnetic field size and intensity for effective WET, a 5 mm-diameter coil with 20 turns was selected as the receiver in our c-LCONs, while a 60 mm-diameter coil with 20 turns was selected as the transmitter for our excitation circuit. The power output between the receiver and transmitter coils are predicted through magnetic field interaction with coil inductance in Figure S8 (Supporting Information) and corresponding coupling efficiencies in Figure S9 (Supporting Information). With an

Figure 2. Analysis of the operation of the c-LCON button with WET. Typical WET parameters were set to 2 MHz operating frequency, while the transmitter was placed in parallel, and 7 mm apart, to the plane of the receiver coil. Experiments where WET was pulsed had an on- and off-period of 10 s each. A) Analysis of the action of WET transfer on the thermal environment and actuation of the c-LCON button, including an (i) annotated IR image heat map of the c-LCON button during WET activation, denoting how the measurement zones were selected based on proximity to the embedded receiver, a (ii) graphical representation of the spatial thermal environment with 2 MHz WET with 8 mm distance between parallel receiver and transmitter, and (iii) overall actuation of the c-LCON button of 7 mm height. B) A finite-element-based simulation of the (i) spatial thermal environment and (ii) actuation of the c-LCON button after WET activation. WET parameters were simulated to be equivalent to operation at 2 MHz, while the transmitter was placed parallel, and 7 mm apart, to plane of the receiver coil. C) Graphical representation of the variable maximum temperature difference within the c-LCON with pulsed WET activation, where the points of WET pulsing are annotated. D) Annotated graphical analysis of stimuli retention time based on spatial thermal data of the c-LCON during pulsed WET activation.

inductance of ≈ 340 nH, the c-LCON receiver has a stimulated coupling efficiency of 0.045 with the excitation circuit; hence, a power transfer of 2.2 W to the receiver is expected when the receiver and the transmitter are adjacent to each other. The greater the coupling efficiency, the greater the rate of energy delivery to the c-LCON and the greater the difference in temperatures between the embedded receiver and the LCON environment. This reduces the period of limited-dispersive behavior of our c-LCONs, as greater temperature differences lead to greater rates of energy transfer through the material and vice versa. The excitation circuit can be programmed to emit radio waves of frequencies between 0.1 and 2 MHz, which serves for a range of coupling efficiencies with our 5 mm receiver coil; coupling efficiency peaks at resonant frequencies, as shown in Figure 3C. Moreover, the extent of WET is inversely proportional to the distance and angle of the receiver with the WET transmitter, as shown in Figure 3D,E; all tests are performed until the c-LCON receiver reaches a maximum temperature. Consequently, we demonstrate that parameters of the excitation circuit can be used to induce adjustable behavior from our c-LCONs, unlocking the potential for self-regulating or oscillating systems based on responsive c-LCON properties.

2.4. Electrically Functionalized Composite Liquid Crystal Oligomer Network Oscillation and Remote Composite Liquid Crystal Oligomer Network Systems

The actuating nature of our c-LCONs can be synergized with the selective energy delivery of WET to achieve self-regulated oscillation. This can be established by the actuation of c-LCON in and out of an active WET stimulus area. The limited-dispersive behavior of thermal stimuli within our c-LCON allows actuation to continue even when our actuator is removed from the WET stimulus area and conversely allows relaxation back into the WET stimulus area without immediate response to actuate it out of the stimulus area. The retention of the thermal stimulus thus establishes two distinct phases, namely energy-harvesting and energy-depleted phases, as depicted in Figure 4A. Fundamentally, the first phase consists of the c-LCON oscillator having the thermal stimulus delivered, retained, and finally inducing actuation, moving the embedded receiver out of the active area and initiating the second phase. In our c-LCON button configuration, actuation leads to a “button-press” that leaves a greater distance between the embedded receiver and the transmitter coil, preventing it from harvesting sufficient energy for continued

Figure 3. WET driving system analysis. A) Schematic of the WET driving system, depicting the (i) power supply contacts, (ii) DC-DC converter, (iii) controller, (iv) heating timer-switch, (v) voltage regulator, (vi) oscillator and gate driver, (vii) class E amplifier and the (viii) secondary capacitor bank. B) Annotated circuit diagram and function map of the WET transmitter system, further described in Table S1 (Supporting Information). C) Graphical comparison of emitted radio-wave frequency of the WET system and the maximum receiver coil temperature increase induced. The WET transmitter was placed 13 mm from the receiver and the coils were kept parallel to each other. D) Graphical comparison of distance between the WET transmitter and receiver and the maximum receiver coil temperature increase induced. The WET system was operated at 2 MHz, while the transmitter was kept parallel to the receiver. E) Graphical comparison of the receiver angle to the WET system transmitter and the maximum receiver coil temperature increase induced. The WET system was operated at 2 MHz, while the transmitter was placed 13 mm apart from the receiver.

actuation. The retained stimulus in the c-LCON gradually dissipates once delivered, causing the c-LCON to eventually relax back to its initial state as it cools. Only once the limited-dispersive period has elapsed, will the c-LCON begin to actuate again, establishing a self-regulating oscillatory behavior as observed in Video S2 (Supporting Information) and depicted in Figure 4A. For our c-LCON configuration with a maximum receiver temperature of 35 °C under the WET field, natural oscillations at 0.027 Hz are achieved, as illustrated in Figure 4B. The oscillation frequency of the c-LCON can be increased by changing the inductance of the receiver coil in the c-LCON to adjust coupling efficiency with the WET system, which would reduce the time spent by the c-LCON in the energy-harvesting phase; this also decreases the c-LCON oscillation amplitude as greater coupling efficiency entails greater rate of energy transfer, which prevents the c-LCON from relaxing in the energy-harvesting region as the receiver temperature increases faster and induces actuation sooner. Using LCON material with higher thermal conductivity would also facilitate faster energy transfer from the receiver coil and faster activation of actuation behavior, leading to smaller amplitude and higher frequency oscillations. Alternatively, the oscillation frequency can be increased by reducing the environment temperature, decreasing the time spent in the energy-depleted phase; the increased heating requirement in a colder environment also increases the c-LCON oscillation amplitude by further

allowing c-LCON relaxation in the energy-harvesting region before the material temperature is sufficiently high to induce actuation. In general, decreasing oscillation amplitude increases oscillation frequency because it entails less time spent in both the energy-harvesting or the energy-depleted domains, as observed in Figure S10 (Supporting Information), and thus be controlled through the same means as oscillation frequency. This oscillation control exhibits the high spatial resolution of WET-driven c-LCONs.

We extend the WET-based selective energy delivery concept for basic material-assisted logical control through the construction of our remotely-operated c-LCON button keyboard. Our demonstrator is operated by the WET-activated self-pressing of c-LCON buttons, which are electrically functionalized with a copper film under the button center in order to connect a simple circuit upon actuation. The force exerted by the “button-press” was optimized to provide sufficient pressure to act as a switch and complete a circuit, as shown in Figure 4C and quantified further in Figure S11 (Supporting Information). This action triggers a connected controller chip to type the letter designated to the c-LCON button within a computer software, demonstrating remote typing by physical rather than digital action, as shown in the schematic in Figure 4D(i). The full keyboard consists of a 3 × 3 c-LCON button array coupled to a controller, the configuration of which is described in Figure 4D(ii,iii). Despite the

Figure 4. c-LCON self-regulated oscillation and keyboard demonstrator. A) Schematic of c-LCON self-regulating oscillation principle, showing the configuration of the c-LCON button when in the (i) energy-harvesting and (ii) energy-depleted zones. B) Graphical analysis of the c-LCON button self-regulating in terms of spatial thermal energy and overall button strain. The WET parameters were set at 2 MHz, while the transmitter was placed parallel, and 8 mm apart, to the plane of the receiver coil. C) Graphical representation of button “press” force with average c-LCON button temperature. D) Annotated schematic of (i) the c-LCON integrated circuit driving the keyboard demonstrator and (ii) an exploded illustration of the 7 cm x 7 cm c-LCON keyboard array including the copper keyboard circuit traces, under-button copper discs enabling interaction of the c-LCON button presses with the underlying circuit, and the 3 x 3 c-LCON button array with (iii) its corresponding image. E) Remote self-pressing c-LCON button for the operation of the c-LCON keyboard demonstrator and its corresponding (i) IR data, (ii) c-LCON button pressing illustration and (iii) corresponding image. The WET parameters were set at 2 MHz, while the transmitter was placed parallel, and 7 mm apart, to the plane of the receiver coil.

proximity of c-LCON buttons in the 7 × 7 cm array, the selective energy delivery allows a single button to be powered as the limited dispersion of thermal stimuli prevents the delivered power from activating neighboring buttons and causing parasitic actuation, as shown in Figure 4E. The actuation control in this system is demonstrated by activating the c-LCON button array in a sequence to spell the string “HIMkey123” as recorded in Video S3 (Supporting Information). Our demonstrator emphasizes the selectivity and stimuli-retention behavior of our c-LCON configurations, despite the miniaturization of the active desired areas.

For both the oscillation and keyboard functions, our LCON material is specifically ideal due to its elastomeric compliance and retention of strong actuation action at low-temperatures; this allows our c-LCON keyboard to be more interactive with human users as a soft robot. The demonstrations in this paper are but one of many potential possibilities for LCON applications; for instance, LCONs offer the ability to incorporate sensing, control, load-bearing and actuation functions into a single material, allowing for self-regulated oscillation based on LCON properties.¹⁰ This highlights the potential of material-assisted logic through stimuli retention and control.

3. Conclusion

We demonstrate the selective and limited-dispersion stimuli delivery of WET systems coupled with c-LCONs, which can be applied to perform c-LCON-regulated oscillations or implement basic material-assisted logic control in devices, such as a remotely-operating keyboard, by localized c-LCON actuation. The next evolution of such a demonstrator would include the individual activation of keys without the requirement for transmitter coil displacement; this can be achieved by designing the receivers in the c-LCON to couple with certain frequencies of WET, which can be adjusted by the controller of the excitation circuit. The sustainable operation of these systems stems from its material-assisted control, which is an intrinsic property of our LC materials and can only be altered chemically or otherwise through adjusting operating frequency and receiver distance and angle parameters in the WET-driving system. Our c-LCONs demonstrate mobile intelligent material behavior and, when coupled with WET, can integrate selectivity and localization in a remotely-activated device for local actuation control and material logic. This is an advance toward engineering remote material-based logic for hybrid circuit designs and could inspire applications in multiple fields, ranging

from remote automated control for medical applications to smart haptic systems for virtual reality.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: 4-(6-(Acryloyloxy)hexyloxy)phenyl 4-(6-(acryloyloxy)hexyloxy)benzoate (reactive liquid crystal monomer, Molecule 1) was used as commercially acquired from Henan Daken Chemical Co. Ltd. Pentaerythritol tetrakis(3-mercaptopropionate) (tetra-thiol crosslinker, Molecule 2) was used as commercially acquired from Bruno Bock Chemische Fabrik GmbH & co. KG). 2,2'-(Ethylenedioxy) diethanethiol (di-thiol crosslinker, Molecule 3) and Glyoxal bis(diallyl acetal) (tetra-vinyl crosslinker, Molecule 4) were used as commercially acquired from and used as commercially delivered from Sigma–Aldrich. Bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)-phenylphosphineoxide (photoinitiator agent Irgacure 819, Molecules 5) was used as commercially received from Ciba Specialty Chemicals NV. 2,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)–4-methylphenol (inhibitor agent BHT) was used as acquired commercially from Sigma–Aldrich. Dipropylamine (basic catalyst for Michael thiol-addition) was utilized as commercially received from Sigma–Aldrich. Chloroform (solvent) was utilized as commercially acquired from Biosolve Chimie SARL. Polyimide-coated copper receiver coils were designed in KiCAD software and assembled by PCBWay.

Liquid Crystal Oligomer Network Synthesis and Coil Compositing: LCON was synthesized using the two-step curing methods. The initial curing step is a Michael thiol additional reaction with a reaction mixture of Molecules 1–4 dissolved in chloroform, catalyzed by the basic dipropylamine. A molar ratio of 10.40:2.49:8.15:1.00 of Molecules 1–4 was included in a typical reaction mixture. 2.5 wt% of photo-initiator and 0.5 wt% of inhibitor molecules were also included in the reaction mixture. This initial reaction results in a polydisperse, thiol-terminated oligomer, as tested in Figure S12 (Supporting Information) via NMR (Bruker), indicated by the lack of peaks between chemical shifts of 6 and 6.5, which would otherwise have been present due to the hydrogens in an acrylate functional group. The polyimide-coated copper coils, with a mass of ≈ 4.94 mg, were placed in the reaction mixture during this first curing step, becoming embedded as the reaction mixture partially polymerized around the coil; the LCON material itself has a mass of 77.7 mg and a sufficiently high actuation force to make the inclusion of the coil have no observable effect on its actuation performance. The partially polymerized material was then brought into its nematic phase by cooling it to 5 °C in a refrigerator. LC alignment was then induced in this material by the use of the stamping method to create c-LCON buttons; the forms for stamping were designed in Solidworks CAD software and manufactured through 3D printing of poly(lactic acid) filament with the Ultimaker S5 printer; as shown in Figure S13 (Supporting Information), this resulted in an order parameter of ≈ 0.47 , measured through the use of dichroic dye and rotated polarizers in a UV–vis spectrophotometer (Perkin–Elmer Lambda 750). The 3 × 3 c-LCON keyboard array was produced by stamping 9 c-LCON buttons and integrating them into a 3D co-polyester casing. LCON was fully polymerized in their aligned states by activating the incorporated photo-initiator molecules through exposure to UV illumination of 250 W m⁻² using a UV-lamp and controller (OmniCure Series 2000), initiating a reaction between the thiol-terminated liquid crystal oligomers and vinyls incorporated into the initial reaction mixture; the use of vinyls with flexible chains disturbs the overall liquid crystal order and reduces the order parameter, yet allows for the reduced initial actuation threshold temperature required for the WET system. Active cooling was applied in the refrigerator to combat the effects of polymerization heating to keep the material at 5 °C and ensure the presence of the nematic liquid crystal phase. Oxygen was removed from the photopolymerizing chamber by flushing the container with nitrogen, preventing any reactions of the photo-initiator molecules with oxygen. The polymerization of the LCONs was evaluated by the absence of thiol groups, which is indicated by the intensity of the S–H bond stretching at wavenumber 2558 cm⁻¹, as shown in Figure S1 (Supporting Information). The final thickness of the resulting c-LCON material is 250 microns; variations with

thicker material are expected to lead to more hindrances for heat dissipation and lead to high stimuli retention times, and vice versa. The reproducibility of the material preparation was enforced by setting tolerances of 2 wt% for each material measured component, while mechanical stretching was performed on a button-shaped mold and the same strain for every c-LCON batch was ensured.

Characterization of Liquid Crystal Oligomer Networks and Coil Composites: Differential scanning calorimetry (TA DSC2500) was used to determine the temperature ranges of liquid crystal phases within the LCON material before alignment and curing; multiple peaks can be caused by the actuation of the aligned LCON in the DSC pan, which was attempted to minimize by pressing the LCON down into the pan to ensure as much contact area and material adherence. The alignment of the material, especially around the integrated coil artifact, was analyzed with polarized optical microscopy (POM, Leica DM2700M). Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (TA DMAQ800) was used to gauge temperature-responsive stress-strain and Young's Modulus of a strip of LCON material, while the c-LCON button "press" force with temperature was measured using a force sensing system (Novatech F329, 4 μN resolution) on a heated stage. The extraordinary expansion coefficient of the LCON was measured to be 0.0165 K⁻¹, while the Young's modulus was recorded to be ≈ 3.8 MPa. The thermal response of the material can only be adjusted in its synthesis by the use of different LC molecules, or in its processing by increasing its order parameter by straining the material more during mechanical alignment. The thermal response rate of the LCON material in the wireless system can be adjusted by changing power and heating rate, while its recovery rate can be influenced depending on the temperature of the environment.

Simulation of Liquid Crystal Oligomer Network Actuation Modes: Thermal activity within the material was modeled by COMSOL software to simulate c-LCON button actuation and spatial thermal properties in the event of Joule heating caused by WET activation, further described in Figures S14–S17 (Supporting Information). High-energy WET parameters were modeled to negate the oscillatory actuation that could otherwise be performed by the c-LCON button.

Wireless Transmitter Design and Analysis: The WET system consists of a class E amplifier powering a tank circuit, the parameters of both are depicted in Figure 3B and the designs are explained in the technical drawings in Figures S5 and S6 (Supporting Information). The designs were drawn with the KiCAD software, while the function of the design was stimulated in LTspice electronic simulation software. Components used, as depicted in the technical drawings, are all commercially available and were used as received from Panasonic, Tracopower, Infineon, Bourns, Harwin, TDK, Farnell, Wakefield Solutions, Murata, Vishay, Taiyo Yuden, ST microelectronics, Cornell–Dubilier, Würth Elektronik, Multicomp, RS, Maxim integrated analog devices and ON semiconductor. A controller chip (Arduino nano) was used to adjust the frequency of the emitted radio waves, and the basic code for which was written in the Arduino design space. The device was powered by a power source with limits of 24 V and 2.5 A (GW-Instek GPE-3323). The emitted radio waves were analyzed by the use of dummy receiver coils connected to an oscilloscope (Keysight DSOX3032T) to calculate the coupling efficiency for different coil sizes through temperature increase generated, measured with the IR camera (Xenith Gobi+ 640) as shown in Figure S18 (Supporting Information), at different distances. As a result of this analysis, c-LCONs were typically placed 7 mm from the transmitter coil and the transmitter was operated at 2 MHz. Despite an expected current draw of 0.6 A, currents of 1.2 A were recorded; this is hypothesized to be due to the induction of eddy currents due to the interaction of the field with other objects in the experimental set-up.

Image Analysis of Composite Liquid Crystal Oligomer Network Actuation Modes: The actuation of the c-LCON systems with time was recorded by taking footage with a camera (Olympus OM-DE-M10 MK3), which was then subsequently analyzed in ImageJ image analysis software. Accompanying IR video was recorded using an IR camera (Xenith Gobi+ 640) and analyzed in IR imaging software (Xenith64) to determine the temperature of the LCON and the embedded coil during experimentation.

Material Design and Construction of Demonstrator Set-Ups: The c-LCON button was implemented in a simple circuit connected to a controller chip (Arduino Due) through the use of Kapton polyimide tape; the

diagram of the simple circuit is illustrated in Figure 4D and was powered using the 5 V native power input of the controller chip. The 3 × 3 c-LCON button array is connected as a demonstrator keyboard via copper film on the center of the inside of the button, closing the circuit, when it comes into contact with the electrically functionalized platform positioned beneath them, to type a character corresponding to the character assigned to the platform; the actuation and relaxation of the c-LCON connects and disconnects the simple circuit respectively. Considering the WET coupling efficiency in this system, the device has an energy conversion efficiency of 4.5%, visualized in Figure S18 (Supporting Information). This translates into a cost of transport of ≈ 1 64 500. This can be significantly reduced, by at least 1 56 000, by increasing WET coupling efficiency. Oscillatory c-LCON actuation was achieved by setting the c-LCON button upside-down above the WET transmitter, causing its motion to increase the distance between itself and the transmitter, reducing the power delivered to the receiver and allowing for material relaxation.

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Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

D.L. performed conceptualization. D.L., M.O.A., and D.V. performed methodology. D.V. and S.W. performed software. M.O.A. performed validation. M.O.A. and D.V. performed formal analysis. M.O.A., D.V., and P.L. performed investigation. D.L. collected resources. M.O.A. performed data curation. M.O.A. wrote the original draft. M.O.A. and D.L. reviewed and edited the author manuscript. M.O.A., D.V., and D.L. performed visualization. D.L. performed supervision. D.L. and M.O.A. performed project administration. D.L. performed funding acquisition.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

electronically functionalized, liquid crystal oligomer networks, self-regulated oscillation, wireless power transfer

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